

Data for Policy 2022

Ecosystems of innovation and
virtual-physical interactions

5 December - Hong Kong

8/9 December – Seattle

13 December – Brussels

Data for Policy 2022

Ecosystems of innovation and virtual-physical interactions

#dataforpolicy2022

Brussels Programme

13th December, UTC+1

Hybrid – In-person and online (U-Residence, VUB and Zoom)

*denotes presenting author

†denotes virtual presentation

08:30 – 09:00 Arrival and Refreshments

09:00 – 09:20 Welcoming Remarks

Green Francesco **Mureddu**, Regional Chair (Lisbon Council)

09:20 – 10:05 A series of ignition talks curated by Francesco **Mureddu**

Green Chair: Rob **Heyman** (imec-SMIT-VUB)

Grace **Milne** (Project Manager and Research Associate at The Lisbon Council) *Satellite Open Data for Smart City Services Development*

George **Beers** (Wageningen Economic Research) *Pathways towards a fair, inclusive and innovative Data Economy for Sustainable Food Systems*

Nathan **Carvalho** (Project Manager at The Lisbon Council) *User-centricity, interoperability and citizens' data sovereignty: the foundations of cross-border digital public services*

Danny **Vandenbroucke** (Research Manager at SADL/KU Leuven R&D) *Urban Data Space for Green Deal*

Karim **Hamza** (Senior Associate Researcher at Vrije Universiteit Brussel) *Data for Africa*

Alessandro **Paciaroni** (Project Manager and Research Associate at The Lisbon Council) *Green responsible privacy preserving data operations along across the edge-core-cloud continuum) was indisposed*

10:10 – 10:55 Green	<p>Session 1a: Standard Track 1a <i>'Data-driven Transformations in Policy and Governance' Panel</i></p> <p>Chair: Martina Barbero (Global Partnership for Sustainable Development Data)</p> <p>[4538] <i>'Data usage improving public policies and policymaking'</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome & Challenges – Zach Smith (Trust-IT, Policy Cloud) • <u>Project Presentations:</u> <p>John Soldatos (TECNE) <i>AI4PublicPolicy</i></p> <p>Antonio Filigrana (ENG) <i>DECIDO</i></p> <p>Cecilia Cabello (FECYT) <i>IntelComp</i></p> <p>Panayiotis Michael (ICCS) <i>Policy Cloud</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on the challenges – Zach Smith and panellists • Q&A from audience • Wrap-up – Zach Smith
10:10 – 10:55 Red	<p>Session 1b: Special Track <i>'The future of Border and external security: From Data to Policies</i></p> <p>Chair: Francesco Leoni (Politecnico di Milano)</p> <p>[3679] Pekka Koskela, Jori Paananen, Anni Karinsalo and Laura Salmela*† (VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd). <i>Enhancing Border Checks with Blockchain towards Self-Sovereign Identity</i></p> <p>[8235] Georgia Gkioka and Gregoris Mentzas (Information Management Unit, ICCS, National Technical University of Athens). <i>Data Analytics for Technology Acceptance Monitoring of SBC Technologies</i></p> <p>[9820] Sara Domingo Andres* and Zachary Goldberg (Trilateral Research). <i>New Technologies for Border Control: Opportunities and Regulatory Challenges</i></p>
10:55 – 11:10	Short break and refreshments
11:10 – 11:55 Green	<p>Plenary Panel <i>'Use of high value datasets for policy making'</i></p> <p>The EU data strategy aims to establish a sustainable framework for the reuse of data to support the development of the single market. Its ultimate goal is to generate economic value and wellbeing. Better access to public sector data is a critical cornerstone of this strategy. This session will focus on recent developments in the EU legal framework to accelerate the reuse of public sector data for evidence-based policy making and the challenges ahead</p> <p>Chair: Emanuele Baldacci (European Commission)</p>

Panelists:

Jon **Crowcroft** (Marconi Professor of Communication Systems, University of Cambridge and The Alan Turing Institute)

Francesco **Mureddu** (Senior Director, Lisbon Council)

Barbara **Ubaldi** (Acting Head of the Division on Open and Innovative Governments, OECD Public Governance Directorate)

*Jean-Claude **Burgelman** (Professor and Academic Coordinator of Open Science Policy, Vrije Universiteit Brussel) was indisposed*

12:00 – 12:45
Green

Session 2a Standard Track ‘(Big) Data for Public Value Creation’
Chair: John **Soldatos** (Netcompany-Intrasoft)

[1000] Maria Claudia **Bodino*** and Athena **Vassilopoulos** (BDTI, European Commission) *Enabling a data-driven public sector: from hype to action using the Big Data Test Infrastructure (BDTI)*

[2505] Gaby **Umbach*** (European University Institute). *Statistical and Data Literacy in Policy-Making*

[6120] Francesco **Leoni*** (Politecnico di Milano). *What makes the “data for policy” discourse different? Analysing themes and topics of the data for policy field*

12:00 – 13:00
Red

Session 2b: Special Track ‘Citizen generated data for policy, innovation and democratic participation’ Workshop

[3290] Suha **Mohamed*** and Vinay **Narayan*** (Aapti Institute) *‘Exploring the possibilities for citizen-generated data and governance models to shape sustainable cities and communities’*

12:45 – 13:45

Lunch and networking

13:45 – 14:30
Green

Keynote Lecture: *The Governance “of with and by” AI: unveiling the future of AI for government*

Abstract: The lecture will present future scenarios on Digital Europe at the horizon 2040, designed as part of the research on ‘Exploring Digital Government transformation in the EU – Understanding public sector innovation in a data driven society’, led by Gianluca Misuraca for the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre. Building on the results of this research and seminal work conducted for the European Commission’s AI Watch on AI for the public sector, as well as research for the Digital Future Society and more recent analysis conducted as part of the AI4GOV project, the presentation will discuss the dilemmas of policy-makers with

regard to what the author defines as the governance “of, with and by” AI, emphasizing the need for a human-centric approach to AI. Addressing the risks and potential of using AI in the public sector, the presentation will outline future research directions and policy recommendations in light of the framework proposed by the EU for leading the digital decade and achieving sustainable development through the twin, green and digital transition of our societies.

Speaker: Gianluca **Misuraca** (Executive Director AI4GOV – Universidad Politécnica de Madrid)

Chair: Emanuele **Baldacci** (European Commission)

14:35 – 15:20
Green

Session 3a Standard Track 2 ‘Data Technologies and Analytics for Policy and Governance’

Chair: Francesco **Mureddu** (Lisbon Council)

[2292] Maedeh **Nasri***, Sarah **Giest**, Yung-Ting **Tsou**, Mitra **Baratchi** (Leiden University), Alexander **Koutamanis** (Delft University of Technology) and Carolien **Rieffe** (Leiden University). *Role of movement data in creating inclusive school settings for students*

[5409] Yulu **Pi*** (University of Warwick) and Cagatay **Turkay** (University of Warwick). *A Multidisciplinary Literature Review and Framework For AI-Assisted Policymaking*

[8550] John **Soldatos***, Thanasis **Papadakis**, Ioannis **Christou**, Charalambos **Ipektsidis** (Netcompany-Intrasoft) and Alessandro **Amicone** (GFT Italia). *AI Solutions for Transparent, Explainable and Regulatory Compliant Public Policy Developmen.*

[8834] Alex **Ingrams***, Sarah **Giest** (Leiden University), Pradeep **Murukannaiah** (Delft University) and Luciano Cavalcante **Siebert** (Leiden University). *The effects of moral framing on crowdsourced comments: The case of regulations.gov*

14:35 – 15:20

Red

Session 3b Standard Track ‘Participatory data collection’

Chair: Antonio **Filograna** (Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.)

[727] Soujanya **Sridharan*** and Shefali **Girish** (Aapti Institute). *Data stewards in service of Artificial Intelligence: Reimagining AI futures towards a participatory paradigm for technological innovation*

[4660] Shradhanjali **Sarma** (Dunzo Digital Private Limited), Utkarsh **Kumar*** (Techpolicy Deck Foundation), Sharanya **Mukherjee** (Techpolicy Deck Foundation) and Shatakshi **Shekhar** (Techpolicy Deck Foundation). *Content Moderation and Freedom of Expression on Social Media*

[5100] Kwawdo **Oti-Sarpong*** (University of Cambridge), Viviana Angeley Bastidas **Melo** (University of Cambridge), Jennifer **Schooling** (University of Cambridge), Li **Wan** (University of Cambridge), Timea **Nochta** (University of Birmingham) and Junqing **Tang** (Peking University). *Digital Innovation in the Urban Built Environment: A Competency Framework for City Managers*

[7081] Morine **Amutorine*** (Data Science Africa). *Increasing data sharing for social good: Lessons from Africa's COVID-19 response*

15:20 – 15:35 Short break and refreshments

15:35 – 16:20 Session 4a: Standard Track ‘Regulatory frameworks and oversight for data sharing’
Green

Chair: Stefaan **Verhulst** (GovLab, NYU)

[5807] Tom **van der Sleen*** (Utrecht University). *Voluntary business-to-government data sharing for advancing SDGs: exploring actor alignment to create mutual benefits*

[8194] Renan Gadoni **Canaan*** (Centre for Law, Technology and Society, University of Ottawa). *Stimulating innovation through data protection regulations: a TWAIL-based de-colonizing critique of the inequity of opportunities for domestic firms arising from replicating EU's GDPR into the Brazilian General Data Protection Law*

[7263] Marika **Arena**, Giovanni **Azzone**, Laura **Dell'Agostino*†** and Giulia **Piantoni** (Politecnico di Milano). *How to measure the innovation ecosystems' shared value? A balanced approach*

[7549] Phil **Godsiff** (INDEX, University of Exeter Business School) and Steve **Brewer*** (University of Lincoln). *Using a data sharing framework for regulatory oversight*

15:35 – 16:20 Session 4b Special Track ‘Public data for private gain or public benefit? Debating the use of public sector data by private actors’
Red

Chairs: Lucille **Tetley-Brown†** (University of Glasgow), Angela **Daly†** (Dundee University) and **Rob Heyman** (VUB)

[118] Amrita **Nanda** (Aapti Institute) and Vinay **Narayan*** (Aapti Institute). *Data stewardship for responsible sharing of public data – an analysis of stewardship models for better urban governance*

[3438] Lucille **Tetley-Brown†** (University of Glasgow), Angela **Daly†** (University of Dundee), Esperanza **Miyake†** (University of Strathclyde) and

Annie **Sorbie***† (University of Edinburgh). *Unlocking public value from personal data? Brokering citizen-centred data-use spaces for the private sector – the Scottish Example*

[4320] Teresa **Scassa***† (University of Ottawa). *Public Sector Use of Private Sector Personal Data: Towards Best Practices*

[4371] Jess **Reia*** (School of Data Science, University of Virginia). *Data for the Night: Digital Rights, Trust, and Responsible Engagement with Data in 24-Hour Cities*

16:25 – 17:15 Closing Plenary Panel: ‘Future avenues in Data for Policy’

Green

Chair: Zeynep **Engin**† (Founder and CEO, Data for Policy and the Alan Turing Institute)

Panelists:

Francesco **Mureddu** (Senior Director, The Lisbon Council)

Barbara **Ubaldi** (Acting Head of the Division on Open and Innovative Governments, OECD Public Governance Directorate)

Stefaan **Verhulst** (Co-Founder and Chief Research and Development Officer, GovLab)

17:15 – 18:45 Networking reception

With thanks to our partner organisations
